

Helicanthe Haptic Multisensory Musical workstation: Application to *Quetzalcoatl*, a musical and visual ongoing artwork

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Abstract. This article summarizes the work in progress we started in the experimental use of the Haptic-Multisensory Helicanthe Workstation developed at ACROE (Grenoble, France) in an ongoing artistic musical work called "Quetzalcoatl" by Claude Cadoz. The Helicanthe workstation integrates high performance force feedback devices, interactive Physics-based Modeling and real time multi-sensory simulation. The musical piece "Quetzalcoatl" is a first artistic experience with two coupled force feedback devices on stage, controlling in real time large physics-based virtual instruments and orchestra.

Keywords: Force-feedback interaction. Real-time multisensory simulation. Real time musical gestures. Physics-based modelling. Virtual Musical Instruments. Computer Music Artwork.

1 The Helicanthe Haptic Multisensory Workstation

Fig. 1. On the left: TELLURIS functional diagram: the real-time simulator (red), the force feedback gestural system with mechanics (blue) and electronics (white), and the audio and video output peripherals. On the right: a view of a future for the Helicanthe workstation, with more than two haptic systems connected to 3D immersive sounds.

The Hélicanthe Platform (Figure 1) is a real-time interactive platform which integrates the five basic technologies developed by ACROE and Grenoble INP into a com-

plete tool for multi-sensory musical and artistic creation, that targets *multisensory interactive situations with force feedback, in which several people can play together, through several haptic devices on a virtual orchestra*. It integrates :

- CORDIS-ANIMA: a modular physical modeling and simulation formalism for multisensory responsive simulation of physical objects [1],
- TGR-ERGOS: "Transducteur Gestuel Rétroactif", mechatronical devices for force feedback gestural interaction [2],
- TELLURIS: which integrates TGRs and a powerful and reactive computer for synchronous multisensory CORDIS-ANIMA simulation [3],
- GENESIS: a software environment dedicated to CORDIS-ANIMA physics-based modeling for sound and musical creation [4], and in particular its new multifrequency version G-IV,
- MIMESIS: a physics-based modeler for Computer Animation [5],
- 24-channel immersive audio and a multi video projection systems.

2 The musical piece "*Quetzalcoatl*" : towards an haptic and multisensory inter-instrumentality

The ongoing musical and multisensory piece *Quetzalcoatl*¹, authored by C Cadoz, is entirely being designed within GENESIS. It sets up a first way of duality: a very large CORDIS-ANIMA model composed of more than 230 000 modules, which is simulated in non real-time, and a sub-part of this model, made of ~5000 modules, which is simulated in real time and played through two TGR force feedback devices of 12 degrees of freedom (DoFs) each. During the performance (Fig. 2), the pre-computed part is displayed acoustically on the 24 audio channels of an immersive sound dome, in synchronicity with the visual display of the 3D movements of all the physics-based model modules, including a real time interactive navigation within the 3D visual scene.

Fig. 2. *On the left:* C. Cadoz and N. Castagné playing "*Quetzalcoatl*" with two force feedback devices on a virtual orchestra at AGORA festival concert in October 2019. Each force feedback device features 12 Degrees of Freedom. The end-effectors morphology is, in that case, a piano keyboard morphology. *On the right:* Screenshot of visualization of simulation in "*Quetzalcoatl*".

The musical performance itself consists in the playing of two performers on two real TGR, playing together with the same instrument.

¹ <https://www.dailymotion.com/video/x7yhpgg>

The Quetzalcoatl piece implements and experiments with a concept of « Inter-Instrumentality ». It consists in virtually coupling the two force feedback devices, by means of physics-based modeling, each of them played by one of the performers. Through the physics-based model, the gesture of each performer can be felt by the other: the artistic exchange between both is achieved not only through the sounds they play, and the visual feedbacks, but also through haptic perception. Such gestural cooperation, beyond the usual audio one, is a very new situation, impossible to reach in real world. This is a new possibility enabled by haptic interaction. Additionally, each performer also interacts with what C. Cadoz calls "emulated gestures": virtual gestures simulated in real time by means of a physics-based model of the gestures. Within Quetzalcoatl, such promising situations are just beginning to be explored.

Conclusion

The *Quetzalcoatl* musical artwork, implemented on the Haptic-Multisensory Hélicanthe workstation, opens new pathways for artistic musical creation, particularly thanks to haptics interaction that restores the sense of touch, which is so ontologically constitutive of Music over ages. Beyond a simple mimetism of traditional instrumental musical situation, new ways are open for Music, such as instrumental gestural cooperation in the context of virtual instruments, between performers, and between performers and virtual gestures achieved with the gestures' emulation method. Such artistic applications, by introducing sensitive and expressive gestures feelings, could be we believe a way to increase acceptability on the side of haptics technologies, for the citizen and the public. However, the necessary technologies must be very efficient, while being accessible to all, which remains a great challenge for the future of Haptic.

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